

The Language Problem Among The Tribes of Tripura: An Overview

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Abstract :-

This paper attempts to explain language & livelihood problems among the tribal people of Tripura. As we know that there are 19 tribes in Tripura speaking different languages, but the majority of them speak Kok-Borok language. But, it is a matter of great concern that Kok-Borok language has no script of its own and is written in either Bengali or in Roman script. It has remained almost confined to non-literary vocabulary among the Tripuri inhabiting hill-slopes or hillocks. A variant of this dialect is also used as a colloquy among the Reangs, Jamatias and Rupinis. The restricted use of this dialect in the form of non-literary colloquy is due to relatively less number of speakers.

This paper justifies language as one of the main causes of the livelihood problem among the tribes of Tripura. The linguistic dominance can be easily observed in this small state in the field of jobs related to administration, politics, culture or education. The tribal people like Debbarmas, staying in and around Agartala, who have adopted Bengali / English language can get better opportunities to qualify as doctor or any white-coloured jobs ; while the Kok-Borok language find no place in the sphere of livelihood matters.

The influence of Bengali language over the Chakma, Mogh, Halam etc. is increasing rapidly, although the dialect differs in many respects from the former. Due to language, the livelihood problem of the tribal people of Tripura is adversely affected.

Key-words- Language, Kok-Borok, Bengali, influence

This paper attempts to explain the language problem among the tribes of Tripura, which proves to be a major issue as far as their livelihood is concerned. As we know that language plays a very pivotal role in the advancement of our knowledge, belief, faith, worship and all round development of personality. This is why, it is an urgent need of the hour to introspect the lives of the tribal people of this tiny state of Tripura.

As per the views of W.W.Hunter, "Ethnographically Tripura stands on a borderland. Tripura has a dual society, a Tripuri society in the eastern hills and a Bengali society in the western valley."(A Statistical Account of Bengal, Vol VI, pp-480). Scheduled tribes constitute about one third of the total population of the state. Altogether 19 Scheduled tribes are recognised throughout the state, who speak different languages, but the majority of

them speak Kok-Borok language. The tribes of Tripura could be divided into 2 major groups:- (1). Ab-original and (2). Immigrants. Tripuri, Reang, Jamatia, Noatia, Lusai, Uchai, Chaimal, Halams, Kukis, Garos, Mog & Chakmas are placed under Ab-original tribes ; while other tribes like Bhil, Munda, Orang, Santhal, Lepcha, Khasi & Bhutias are the immigrant tribes.

It is said that India is a forest of languages. Suniti Kumar Chatterjee rightly defines, “A language is a group/set of words that are produced, by means of sounds pronounced with the organs of speech, used in a particular community, placed independently or used in sentences and used for the expression of thought.” Linguistically, the tribes of Tripura can be divided into 3 groups:- (1). Bodo groups, (2). Kuki-Chin groups & (3). Arakan groups. Tripuri, Reang, Jamatia, Uchai and Noatias are Mongloid tribes and belong to Bodo linguistic group of tribes. Kukis, Lusai and most of the tribes under Halam tribes linguistically belong to Kuki-Chin group and speak in Kuki-chin language. Mog and Chakma fall under Arakan group and speak in Arakan language.

We know that education plays a significant role in human life. Without education, a person is considered as uncivilised and uncultured. According to A.W.B. power, the first political agent of Tripura, “The people were virtually without any education. While the hill people were totally illiterate, the people of the plains were marginally better. There were only two schools in the Raja’s territory, one at Agartala known as ‘Anglo-Vernacular school, or the Maharaja’s school and the other at Kailasahar, which was opened only in 1872.” As the matter of fact, it was the able reign of Birchandra Manikya that for the first time elementary education was started for both boys and girls in 1872 A.D. and written laws were also introduced and the domestic slavery was prohibited in 1878 A.D. Under the patronage of Bir Chandra Manikya ‘Rajaratnakaram’, a well-known historical work was published. During this time, Dinesh Chandra Sen has written ‘ Vanga Bhasa O Sahitya’, the history of Bengali literature.

As a matter of fact, language is an important marker in fastening the ethnic identity. It is a rallying point and an important symbol of group- consciousness and solidarity. A language conflict invariably leads to an ugly political issue. Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India has rightly said, “Language should not be a dividing factor, but it should bring us together and each language can help the other languages of India grow through contact and exchange of ideas.” Despite Nehru’s lofty thoughts, the government did not pay heed to these languages. About 420 languages and dialects of different language families are used in a complex and wide- ranging ethno and socio- linguistic configuration of North East India. This fact confers a certain singularity and distinctness to language-related issues in the region. The ethnic spectra of North- East India encompass the non-tribal population as well as the tribal population belonging to 209 Scheduled tribes of this region. (Samuel, John, ‘Language and Nationality in North-East India’ in ‘Economic & Political Weekly Vol- 28, No-3-4, pp-91-92).

A great writer S. N. Chatterjee observes, "In Tripura, altogether 96 languages have been identified. Of these numerically, Bengali, Tripuri, Reang, Chakma, Jamatia, Hindi, Manipuri are important. Bengali is spoken by 67% of the population of the state and is recognised as official state language. The next important language is Tripuri, spoken by about 17% of the total population of the state."(Chatterjee, S.N., Tripura: A profile, Inter-India Publications, New Delhi, 1984, p-44). This is why, in a pluralistic society of Tripura what is remarkable is not just the numbers and variety of dialects, but that each one of them reflect a distinctively definable community having distinctive traits, traditions, attitudes, beliefs, customs and habits. Sometimes, a combination of the dialects spoken in a homogenous territory having some common characteristic traits develops into a language. A language in conjunction with culture, religion and history is an important component of nationality formation. Its functional and symbolic value has far reaching significance in the transitional continuum from continuity to ethnicity and from ethnicity to formalized nationality.

Empirical study on the basis of historical evidences show that no aboriginal tribal communities of Tripura had their own written script, all being in a form of colloquial expression. So, the rulers of Tripura had to look for a written Language for the sake of administrative works. It is stated that Bengali, the flourishing language of the neighbouring plain land was adopted as the state language of Tripura. (Deb, Dasharath, why Bengali script is needed for writing kok-Borok ?, ICAT, Govt. of Tripura, Agartala, 1995, p-17).

'Dialects' are indeed part and parcel of a language. There can be many dialects within a given language. It might be said that this divergence of dialects was inevitable in earlier times, when communication was remote. Despite this, it is also likewise that one finds similarities between the distinctive characteristics of geographically contiguous dialects or speeches. The dialect of the Tripuris is known as 'Kok-Borok', the literal meaning of which is the language of men. It is one of the Bodo groups of dialects which had originated in the Brahmaputra valley and which was at one time spoken over a wide area in that valley and the adjoining areas of north Bengal as well as east Bengal, forming a solid block in North-eastern India. The dialect belongs to the Sino – Tibetan speech family. But, it is a matter of great concern that Kok-Borok language has no script of its own and is written in either Bengali or in Roman script. We can say that it has remained almost confined to non –literary vocabulary among the Tripuri inhabiting hill-slopes or hillocks. A variant of this dialect is also used as a colloquy among the Reangs, Jamatias and Rupinis.

If we look at the past history of Tripura, we find that from the earliest days of its growth, Bengali has found a place of honour in the royal court of Tripura. Till the integration of Tripura with the Independent India, Bengali had functioned as the official language of Tripura. It is understood that the kings of Tripura had adopted Bengali as the language of the royal family, by which a new culture among the tribal people could be witnessed. Later on, the tribal people of Tripura started to speak in Bengali instead of their mother tongue Kok-Borok. They seemed to be engaged in other Bengali culture pursuits like literature, dance, music, rites and rituals etc.

History is the evidence of this fact that Kok-Borok, a Tibeto- Burmese speech of Tripura was a majority language of the tribal population of the state prior to merger of Tripura with India after independence. At present, we find that of the total population of Tripura, the Kok-Borok speaking tribal communities occupy the majority. Out of 19 tribal communities of the tribal population of the state, 8 communities viz. Tripuri, Reang, Noatia, Jamatia, Rupini, Koloi, Uchoi and Murasing speak in Kok-Borok. Apart from the Kok-Borok speaking tribal communities, other minor tribal communities of this state use Kok-Borok language as the medium of communication amongst the tribal communities each other. In the recent past, the Halam communities call the language of Kok-Borok as 'Rajani-Kok' or 'language of the kings'. Kok- Borok language is the sister language of Boro, Dimasa, Garo etc. As such, there is no doubt about the oldness of this language.

Significance of Kok- Borok Language & literature

We find that out of the total tribal population of Tripura, the Kok-Borok speaking tribal communities occupy the majority. According to the census of 1991, the tribal population in the State stood 8, 53,345 out of 27, 57,205 being the total population of the State. Out of the total tribal population, the Kok-Borok speaking tribal population comprising the above mentioned eight communities is presumed to be about seven lakhs.

At present, we can assess that Kok-Borok language has been recognised as a language of literature. Therefore, it deserves a language of lively amplitude and distinctive originality. The linguists are of the view that if the modern method of the Linguistics is followed, then the development of this language is certain.

We find that the first Kok-Borok magazine was published in the mid of fifties. From the seventies, there is a continuity of development process and activities in creating Kok-Borok literature. Though, there is still dispute in matter of Kok-Borok script and spelling method, the number of publication of Kok-Borok books on poems, short stories, novel, drama and books of translation are gradually increasing and has taken an important position.

The State Government of Tripura has recognised Kok-Borok as one of the official languages of the state in 1979 A.D. The important Govt. notifications, publicity booklets etc. are being published in the Kok-Borok language along with Bengali. The Kok-Borok language was introduced as a medium of instruction for the Kok-Borok speaking students at the primary stage about twenty years back and it has now been extended up to degree level classes.

The development of Kok-Borok Language & literature

- It is stated that Radhamohan Thakur has written the Grammar of Kok-Borok named as 'Kok-Borokma,' which was published in 1900 A. D.

- Traipur Kothamala ,the Kok-Borok-Bengali-English translation book has also been written by Radhamohan Thakur and was published in 1906.
- ‘KOK-BOKMA’, the Kok-Borok grammar book was written in 1897 A. D. Jointly by two authors named as Daulot Ahmed and Md. Omar.
- The first Kok-Borok Magazine "Kwtal Kothoma" was first edited and published in 1954 by Sudhanwa Deb Barma, who was one of the founder of the Tripura Janasiksha Samiti, and a social worker and a political personality of the State.
- Sudhir Krishna Deb Barma had written two Kok-Borok Books named as ‘Koktang’ and ‘Surungma Yakhili’, which were published in 1954 and 1962 respectively.
- Kok-Borok Dictionary named as ‘Kokrobam’ was written by Ajit Bandhu Deb Barma, which was published by the Education Directorate in 1967.
- The Kok-Borok text Book for children ‘Cherai Surungma (Bagsa)’ was published by the Education Directorate in 1958, which was written by Mahendra Deb Barma.
- A number of Kok-Borok and Bengali Magazines were patronizing the thoughts and aspirations of the tribal people. Some of those were —
 - (i).Koktun, edited by Ajoy Deb Barma and Surjya Reang,
 - (ii).Chini Kok, edited by Ajoy Deb Barma & subsequently by Nirmal Deb Barma
 - (iii).Tripura Kogtun, a Kok-Borok mouthpiece of the Information Cultural Affairs and Tourism Department of the Government of Tripura, edited by Shyamlal Deb Barma
 - (iv).Yapri, edited by Narendra Deb Barma of Kok-Borok and tribal culture, One — "Tripura kok-Borok Unnayan Parisad" was established under the Chairmanship of Bir Chandra Deb Barma in 1967.
- Tripura Kok-Borok Sahitya Sabha was founded by Sailendralal Tripura, which organised regular discussion on the kok-Borok development and tribal culture through Annual conference, Seminars etc.

Problems faced by the Kok-Borok people in terms of livelihood

The tribal people of Tripura, who come under the category of ‘Scheduled tribes’ in terms of the provision of the Constitution of India are facing a lot of problems in terms of livelihood, because their Kok-Borok language is not sufficient for providing them the opportunities in job market. This is why, We observe that the HDI (Human Development Indices) of tribal population is quite low as compared to the rest of the population of the state. This is also mainly because they live in clusters generally in far flung areas, which are remote or in the vicinity of forests and consequently enjoy an effective isolation from the main stream of the country. Their more or less isolated life prevents them from exploiting many advantages of modern civilization. The development programme meant for the general public often elude the tribal population for the reasons of inaccessibility and difficult terrain. K.S.Singh has rightly pointed out, “The tribals are dispossessed of their land, forest, trade and commerce and

finally of their culture of which language and dialect are vital modes, unlike the inhabitants of any other North- Eastern state the original of Tripura, both tribals and non-tribals have been submerged by the growing mass of the non-tribals, neutralising the process of acculturation. (Singh, K.S., Ethnicity, Identity and Development, The Fourth Verrier Elwin Lecture, 1985, Shillong, Maohar, New Delhi, pp- 23-27).

Nevertheless the Government of India and the State Governments have taken a number of measures over the years to improve the conditions of STs and for their development. But a lot more needs to be done. The linguistic dominance can be easily observed in this small state in the field of jobs related to administration, politics, culture or education. The tribal people like Debbarmas, staying in and around Agartala, who have adopted Bengali / English language can get better opportunities to qualify as doctor or any white-coloured jobs ; while the Kok-Borok language finds no place in the sphere of livelihood matters.

At this juncture, I intend to state that simply recognising 'Kok-Borok' language as one of the official languages of this state will not be sufficient for the welfare of the tribal people of Tripura. This language must be made a 'language of livelihood' for the tribal people; only then it will pave their future. On the contrary, it will be simply a language of the library.

Strategies to be focussed on vocationalisation of Kok-Borok language

Article '46' of the Constitution of India states, "The state shall promote with special care the education and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and in particular of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, and shall protect them from social injustices and all forms of social exploitation."

This is why, it is the great need of the hour that we should look into the matters of the tribal people of this state. A lot of Government policies have been made to upgrade their status by means of providing them ample scholarships and reservations of the seats in the employment. But, who takes the benefit of these welfare measures? Generally, among the tribal people, the persons who are from affluent families and receive their education in a reputed institutions in English/ Bengali medium. Therefore, Kok-Borok language must be given due preference in the matters of vocationalisation. I mean to say that from the high school onwards the students must be imparted the vocational training along with their normal studies.

The tribal people, who dwell in the far flung remote hilly areas, are mostly deprived of the essential requirements of normal human beings. Such as: - food, shelter, clothing, health, education etc. If we want that they should also lead a comfortable life, then we must think of their real problems in a practical manner as Mahatma Gandhi, the father of the nation had always insisted that India would become truly independent only when the poorest of its people would be free from sufferings. How to feed their stomach?- is a burning

question in front of them. Therefore, the tribals of the hilly and dense forest areas should be well-trained in acquiring their means of living, i.e., 'the livelihood skills' in a better manner.

Suggestions to improve the socio-economic condition of the tribal people

Though Tripura ranks first in the literacy rate as per the latest statistical data, but still the socio- economic condition of the tribal people inside dense forest and in the remote hilly areas is pathetic. The followings are the suggestion to improve their socio-economic condition:-

- The Government should start English medium schools in the remote tribal villages in order to provide the tribal students a lot of opportunities in terms of job.
- The teacher- student ratio should be maintained in a proper manner for quality education.
- In- service training for teachers should be started to improve the quality of education.
- Model residential schools should be started in each block, where the poor rural S.T. students should be imparted free and compulsory education like their urban fellows.
- The small scale industries should be started in the tribal areas.
- The students should be imparted vocational training such as the bamboo- work, embroidery etc.
- The proper education of the information technology should be imparted to the rural S.T. students from the high school onwards.
- Government English medium colleges should be opened to provide the tribal students a lot of opportunities in the higher education.
- At the same time they must be imparted the education of Kok-Borok language to retain their rich cultural heritage and eternal tradition.

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